

Teaching Competencies

Abstract

Teaching Competency is the acquisition and demonstration of composite skill required for student teaching to exhibit the various types of skills and to explore the intelligence in an effective way. It refers to a set of abilities and capabilities in the development of its teaching to the scope of teaching competency related to interaction with students, creating a learning environment, good lesson designing and to employ varied teaching strategies with good communication skills. Here the teacher should be so much competent to role play and to enhance the competency level. There are some suggestions by NCTE to adopt to improve the competency level, contextual competency, context-related competency, transitional competency, activity-related competency, development of teaching learning materials competency, evaluation competency, management competency, working with community and other agencies in the view of the above personality skills also play a major role in the teaching learning field. Here the teachers should use some popular tools, technological gadgets and some models in this way the teacher may develop the competency level.

Keywords: Competency, Democrat, Evaluation, Professionalism, Ever Note, Implication

Introduction

Teaching competencies are the acquisition and demonstration of the composite skill required for student teaching like introducing a lesson. Fluency in questioning, probing questions, explaining the pace of lesson, reinforcement, understanding child psychology, recognizing behaviour, classroom management and giving assignments. Competency development must be a continuous process in the organization. Encyclopedia dictionary of education describes teaching competency as the state of having demonstrated skills, abilities or aptitudes in the satisfactory execution of learning tasks. Encyclopedia or teacher training and education defines teaching competency as suitable for sufficient skills, knowledge and experience for teaching purposes properly satisfied.

Aim of the Study

To develop the competencies among the teachers with different types of tools and techniques including the evaluation procedure in the form of a teaching strategy for the inculcation of heuristic spirit in teaching with various types of parameters including the training programme also with some in-service programmes.

Meaning

Teaching competency refers to the set of abilities and capabilities, values and beliefs, attitudes and temper. And knowledge and skills that a teacher possesses towards teaching competency is the degree of knowledge and skills, personality traits that a teacher possesses towards his worthy teaching profession to make himself a good teacher. The teaching competencies are identified in terms of mastery competencies are identified in terms of mastery over the content. Communication skills, classroom behavior, problem solving, equality, personality traits, relationship with student and society, compassion of profession etc. Teaching competency means an effective performance of all observable teacher that brings out desired pupil outcomes.

Scope of Teaching Competencies

Being a teacher at any level requires a significant amount of knowledge and skill. Paying attention to the core competence for educators helps to ensure that all teachers and others who work in education are prepared to make school a positive experience for students and their families a positive experience for students and their families.

Interacting with Students

Educators must be able to positively interact with all students, this includes difficult students who work below grade level and students whose personalities just put aside their prejudices and feelings in order to treat

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all students with respect. Provide them with equal opportunities for learning and make them feel confident.

Create a Learning Environment

Creating a safe learning environment that is conducive to learning is essential. Educators must set high expectations for student performance and behavior. All rules must be enforced consistently and fairly.

Good and at Lesson Plan Design

All educators must be capable of designing lesson plans to meet students' needs and cover the standards. This requires knowing how to choose and create instructional material to accommodate students at different levels. It also requires creating a scope and sequence that provides students with enough time to master the standards.

Able to Employ Varied Teaching Strategies

Best practices and other appropriate teaching strategies allow competent educators to effectively teach the curriculum. Competent educators use any lecture but they also incorporate a variety of strategies. Including non-traditional teaching strategies to help students with multiple learning styles learn and stay engaged. Educators also attend regular professional development sessions to learn new strategies and the latest best practices.

Use of Assessment Well

Educators must design, select, and administer effective assessments. An assessment must accurately measure what has been taught and what students have learned. Competent educators combine informal and formal assessment techniques to monitor students' performance. They also incorporate technology, portfolios, and other creative methods to assess students.

Good at Communications

Communicating effectively with parents and other stakeholders in a child's education is a key component of an educator's job. A quality educator provides regular updates on a child's progress and immediately addresses any concern that may arise. Educators also know how to calmly discuss issues with difficult parents and how to come to decisions that have the best interests of the child in mind.

Significance of Teaching Competencies

1. It helps the teacher to master over the subject matter.
2. It improves the effectiveness of teaching.
3. It increases the quality of education.
4. It helps the teacher to set up achievable objectives of classroom.
5. It develops good communication skills.
6. It develops good relationship with students, parents, and society.
7. It creates appropriate atmosphere for teaching learning process.
8. It helps the teacher to have good personality.
9. It helps the teacher to develop research attitude, creativity, innovative mind.
10. It motivates the teacher to design curricular and co-curricular activities.
11. It develops the good leadership qualities.

Role of Teacher

Confident

A teacher is expected to win and share the confidence of the students.

Democrat

A teacher is expected to be the promoter of Democratic values.

Detective

He detects rule breaker students.

Facilitator of Learning

A teacher is expected to promote effective learning in the students.

Friend and Philosopher

He should act as a friend to all students.

Group Leader

He is expected to act as a leader in developing cohesion and suitable climate in the class as a social group.

Helper

The teacher is expected to be a helper of students, providing them academic and personal guidance.

Judge

A teacher is expected to evaluate the achievement of the student in a fair and judicious manner.

Inspire and Example

He is expected to behave in a manner that students get inspiration from him.

Common Teaching Competencies

Competency I

Subject matter knowledge: the effective early childhood, elementary middle or secondary school teacher demonstrates knowledge.

1. The subject matter of early childhood, elementary middle or school education including literature and the language arts, mathematics, social studies, the arts, health, and physical education.
2. Mastery over the particular subject that has to be taught.
3. The physical, social, emotional, intellectual, and moral development of adolescents, both with and without special needs.
4. Multidisciplinary, students' teaching, and interdisciplinary planning.
5. The relationships among the disciplines taught in the middle secondary school.

Competency II

Communication Skill

The Effective Teacher

1. Communicative sensitively with language appropriate to students' ages, level of development, gender, race, and ethnic linguistic and socio-metric backgrounds, as well as individual learning backgrounds, individual learning styles, and needs.
2. Impressive communication, effective language skills.
3. Interacts with students, effective families, and colleges.

Competency III**Instructional Practice****The Effective Teacher**

1. Understands typical and typical development and is familiar with principles of curriculum including strategies for interacting special education student in the regular classroom setting and developing and implementing individualized educational plans.
2. Teachers through diverse modes, including new technologies, reading and language arts, as appropriate to age. Learning style and developmental stage of the learner works effectively with families and community sources.
3. Makes curricular content relevant to the experience of students from diverse racial socio economic , linguistic and cultural backgrounds
4. Organizes and manages a classroom to support the growth and learning of diverse students.
5. Uses methods that develop students academic and social skills.

Competency IV**Evaluation****The effective teacher**

1. Designs and uses various evaluative producers to assess student learning.
2. Evaluates his or here own teaching behavior and uses the results to improve student learning.

Competency V**Problem solving****The effective teacher**

1. Think critically about teaching and learning
2. Forests students creative and analytical thinking skills.

Competency VI**Equality**

1. Deals equitably and responsibly with all learners.
2. Understands the impact western and you westry civilization on contemporary. Indian culture and uses this knowledge to develop appropriate strategies.

Competency VII**Professionalism**

1. Understands his or her legal and moral responsibilities
2. Learns from experience an supervisors
3. Understands the impact of societal problems that can effect student learning negatively and uses appropriate strategies to address such issues.

Competency VIII**Personality**

1. Impressive personality
2. Sense of human and self analysis
3. Aesthetic and artistic outlook
4. Good attitude and aptitude
5. Love for the student
6. Patience and tolerance
7. Standard ethics conduct and character
8. Friendly nature and co-operative mind.

Ten Teaching competencies by NCTE

The national council of teacher educational identified ten teachers competencies for making the teachers professionalism content. These are discussed below in brief.

Contextual Competencies

One of the first and foremost obligations of teacher is to ensure that whether the parents and community are accepting the importance and usefulness of their efforts. , for this teachers should have the ability to understand various context such as historical background present status of socio-economic. Culture linguistic and religious context of the family milieu and the community profile. They should be able to conduct survey fro finding out reason for poor cantonment poor performance and causes of certain problems like wastage and stagnation etc. which Hindu the process of educatory.

Conceptual Competencies

The teacher should have competencies identities under it are clarity of thought deep understanding of educational theories and through knowledge various educational terms.

Pedogocial methods and techniques etc.

1. They should know significant characteristics of child development at different stages enable them to transact curriculum effectively
2. They should have knowledge of classroom organization and management too which would help them in organizing curricular and co-curricular activities quite effectively in and outside classroom.
3. Concepts and educational implications of globalization modernization, liberalization privatization have to be understood by teachers.

Content Related Competencies

These includes are

1. Full mastery over the content of the subject that they have to teach.
2. They should find out the hard sots and gaps in curriculum which require explanation and elaboration.

Transactional Competencies

1. Educational transactional competency refers to the skill of day to day teaching to achieve educational objectives efficiency through meaningful interaction between teachers and pupils and the environment by using different methods activities and technology in an integrated and effective manner.
2. To organize verity of activities such as story telling singing games, field visit celebration of national, social and cultural events to make teaching learning participatory and relevant.
3. To prepare appropriate teaching aids and other teaching learning material to support and enhance the effectiveness of teaching learning process.
4. To integrate continuous evaluation while transacting subject content.
5. To identify the weaker and brighter children in order to adopt remedial measures and undertake enrichment programs.

Educational Activities Related Competency

The curricular activities are expected to promote cognitive development of children as well as non cognitive development. so here the competencies required by a teacher are.

1. Ability to organize curricular and co- curricular activities for achieving educational objectives
2. Ability to organize social and cultural activities like morning assembly, days celebration etc.

Competencies to Develop Teaching Learning Material

It includes,

1. Ability to develop interesting teaching aids for making learning process easy. Interesting and activity based.
2. Ability to develop textural and self learning material for children as per the age and nature.
3. Knowledge as how to develop work books and activity books.

Evaluation Competencies

It involves the ability of a teacher to continuously judge and verify the level of achievement of prescribed competencies and objective laid down in the curriculum on the part of student is generally referred to as evaluation competency.

1. Teacher should be able to carryout continuous evaluation in a systematic and formal manner.
2. Ability to undertake action research.
3. Competencies related to working with parents.
4. It is the ability of a teacher to get the co-operation of parents and their involvement for achieving the objectives. It implies the abilities to discuss various problems that children with their parents face and suggest some workable solutions.

Management Competencies

1. It involves the skill of the teacher to achieve high quality educational objectives in minimum time. Energy and money through appropriate and effective use of educational aids and active participation of available human resources.
2. Every teacher is a manager of particular class or group of student.
3. Teacher should have the skill classroom management including total teaching as well as subject teaching in the class.

Competencies related to Working with Community and Other Agencies

To improve the standard of educational in schools, teacher needs to seek co- operation and support of members of the community as well. Teacher must have the ability to work towards bringing school and the community as close as possible stand the role of the community in the development of the school and must community at large can contribute to regular and effective functioning of the school and its continuous growth.

Components of Teaching Competencies

We can categories components of teaching competencies in to five kind.

Competency in Personal

1. He / she process and good physical fitness
2. He/she should always be active
3. They should possess eligibility
4. They should possess positive attitude towards students and teaching
5. Personality they should possess awareness.

Competency in professional

1. Deep knowledge about teaching of content possess and using appropriate teaching skill adopting now innovative method and techniques is classroom teaching
2. Possess discovery attitude

Competency in social

1. They should competent enough to criticizes openly.
2. Achieving the specific objectives in instruction
3. They should possess good leadership qualities
4. Working with co-operatives.

Competency in planning

While planning and preparing for teaching the teacher should possess certain competences as follows.

1. Construction of objectives
2. Selection of teaching methods.
3. Analyze of content
4. Content selection
5. Preparation of teaching material
6. Preparations of evaluation tools

Competency of interaction in classroom

Teacher while interacting with students they should possess following competency.

1. Diagnosis
2. Control
3. Motivate
4. Discuss
5. Presentation evaluation
6. Questioning
7. Providing feedback
8. Answering

Characteristic of Teacher with Different Knowledge and Personality Skills

Teaching is a hard work and some teachers never grow to be anything better than mediocre they do the bare minimum required and very little more . The greater teaches however, work tirelessly to create a challenging nurturing environment for their students.

A great Teacher Respects Students

In a great teachers classroom, each persons ideas and opinions are valued. Student feel safe to express their feelings and learn to respect creates a welcoming learning environment for all students.

A great teacher creates A Sense of Community and Belonging in The Classroom.

The mutual respect in this teachers classroom provides a supportive collaboration environment in this small community there are rules to follow and jobs to be done and each student . is aware that he or she is an important integral part of the group.

A Great Teacher has his Own Love of Learning

It inspires students with his passion for education and for the course material He constantly renews himself as a professional on his quest to provide student with the highest quality of educational possible this teacher has no fear of learning new technologies in to lessons, and always seems to be the one who is willing to share what he's learned with colleges.

A Great Teacher is a Skilled Leader

Different from administrative leaders, effective teachers focus on shared decision making and team work as well as on community building. Opportunity for each of them to assume leadership roles.

Popular Teaching Tools to Improve The Teaching Competencies**Google Apps for Education**

Its no surprise that Google once again reigns supreme. Google claims that more than 40 million students and educators use its suite free apps, and why wouldn't they? Google apps for education include tool like Google docs, which helps student and teachers collaborate, and a calendar that helps student and teaches stay organized the customizable security setting Lind peace of the mind and its all ad free.

Word Press

Last year. Word press came in at number of on our list, but this year we moved this platform to the number six sport because of its value of educators, Teachers can start a classroom blog that all students can continued to this encourages them to think deeply about what they are learning and engage discussion at also serves as a fun way to help to writing skills.

Evernote

Evernote proudly points out that it has more than 100 millions users. A good number of the app to share in formation with students and substitute teachers. Organize lesson plan and jot down ideas . the tags and reminders features can help you stay on schedule and on top of all your material. last year ever note came in at no five on the list and the only reason it dropped a few places is because there are so many other awesome teaching tools that merit a mention.

Drop Box

Drop box is another cloud storage service that gives you easy access to your document at any time and any place. All you have to do is drag a file or folder into drop box and it syncs across all your devices even though it was number six on our list last year this app taken to the 10th spot because Google drive has usurped much of its functionality.

You tube

What student wouldn't choose to watch you tube rather than read a textbook?

This video sharing flat form is a universe in it self with myriad channel that can help educators, among the most popular channels that are bound to capture students attention is shorts of Awe, which presents fascinating facts about a range of scientific topics. For its ever growing uses funless. You tube move top up a spot in the form last year first.

Improving the Competence of Teaching in Educational Measurements

It is one of the most importance to educational progress that the competence of teachers to measure educational attainments be improved for more harm, perhaps ten times as much harm, is currently being done to student learning as a result of the short comings of classroom tests by which a students , educational efforts are largely stimulated directed and evaluated then is being done

by all the facts of cocternal testing porogramme, let us concede that some facts do exist in external testing programmes faults of caergon of duplication and of misuse of test results let as also concede that these faults detract from the great service that external testing programmes can render to education but let us not allow thee recognition of this mote to distract our attention from the beam. This mote I am fully proceeded that the current the attention is testing which more urgently requires the attention of all professional educators is that of improving the tests made and used by the classroom teacher.

To establish the importance of improving teacher competence in measurement . It is necessary to show not only that measurement of Educational attainments is needed and possible but also that teachers are currently deficient in getting this job done. I know of litel objective date which would confirm this critical view of teacher competence this critical view of teacher competence in measurement it does, however seem to be quire generally supported by the opinions of all concerned measurement , specialists, school administrators, students , parents, even by the teachers them selves.

Teaching Competencies for Science Teacher

Recently I has been realised that there is a need of constructivism inspired teaching where science teachers are the intermediate agents b/n learners and curriculum, the teacher lived experience in order to mediate turn to shape of the learning UNESCO Regional office. Bang KOK has developed a list of science teachers competence which are mentioned in brief.

1. Competences as related to laboratory procedures and techniques
2. Competencies as related to laboratory produces and techniques.
3. Mathematical competencies :
4. performing educational skills
5. Translate words, symbols statements
6. Construct three dimensional geometrical figures
7. Perform interactive skills

Competencies as related to the Case of Educational Technology

1. Describe the use of following in teaching
2. Instructional modules
3. Inquiry techniques
4. Investigate laboratory activities
5. Individualized instruction techniques
6. Lesson which reflect the processes of science

Educational Fundamentals

A science teacher should have an understanding of the principles of education such as

1. Describe the nature of science, its impact on society.
2. Explain the need and meaning of scientific technological literacy.
3. Explain the meaning of teaching of scientific testing minimum level of learning grading.
4. Explain the recent and relevant learning theories, such as construstivistic view of learning , cognitive development
5. Develop the instrumental material

Educational Implications

Competent teachers are required in every educational institutions so as to increase the effectiveness of the institution, it is necessary to know about professional commitment and how it is influenced by other variables.

Teaching competencies of the teacher is not dependent on the job satisfaction but frequent workshops or interaction. With experts can of room the competencies required by the teachers.

The present studies reveals that commitment is influenced by the work situation and satisfaction of the teachers in those working conditions.

Satisfaction from the job is necessary for full devotion and commitment of teachers towards the profession.

School authorities should identify the ways and means through which teachers can be provided with facilitating work environment which will influence their work.

Conclusion

Teaching is a profession that encompasses the passion and desire to motivate and encourage children to develop a lifelong love of learning. It has many challenges but also provides man rewards children are inspirational in their desire to large from those around them and should be valued for contribution they make to the world. Teachers are facilitators and guides on the Childs journey for

developing essential skills and knowledge to become valued and worth while members of the community.

Teachers need to have a philosophy of teaching that reflects their own teaching that reflects their own personal beliefs about how much children learn. How to manage behavior how to establish an effective and festive classroom and how they will integrate teaching and learning strategies into class room. A teacher has the opportunity to make a difference in the lives of children therefore needs to be committed to developing essential knowledge skill and attributes to faster this important role.

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